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THE ECONOMICS OF RENEWABLE ENERGY AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: This article examines Uzbekistan's efforts within the framework of its transition to a green economy, focusing on the current state and future prospects for the utilization of renewable energy sources. It analyzes the impact of the expanding renewable energy sector, driven by global initiatives and international agreements, on the country's economic growth. As part of "Uzbekistan's 2019–2030 Green Economy Transition Strategy", various measures are being implemented to enhance the effectiveness of green economy mechanisms in achieving sustainable development. Additionally, the article provides practical recommendations and conclusions on accelerating the transition to a green economy.

Key words: green economy, green investments, renewable energy, environment, energy.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, climate change is being strongly observed worldwide. Issues such as resource scarcity, environmental pollution, food security, and water shortages are prevalent across the globe. The world's population is growing, and the number of entrepreneurs is increasing. In recent years, Uzbekistan has also witnessed a rise in both its population and entrepreneurial activities. Ensuring the provision of energy resources and implementing energy-saving technologies has become a crucial challenge. At the same time, it is essential to further promote the widespread use of renewable energy sources and strengthen their legal framework.

This article provides an overview of the ongoing efforts in Uzbekistan. For instance, significant initiatives are being carried out under the framework of the "Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Transition to a Green Economy for 2019–2030." Notably, measures such as attracting green investments, fostering international cooperation, utilizing renewable energy sources, and preventing environmental pollution play a critical role in the successful implementation of this strategy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Need for Transition to a Green Economy: Mechanisms and Specific Principles – Author: Berdiyurov Bakhtiyor Sodiqovich. This article discusses the necessity of transitioning to a green economy, its mechanisms, and specific principles.

Ecological Problems and Strategic Directions for Environmental Management – Authors: Ashurov M. S., Shakirova Yu. S. This monograph examines the direct correlation between sustainable economic development

and a balanced approach to environmental and economic issues. It explores the impact of environmental balance on economic stability, their interdependence, the institutional and legal aspects of environmental management, and strategic directions for assessing and addressing environmental challenges.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs observation, generalization, analysis, and comparison methods to examine the ongoing developments in the energy sector and the utilization of renewable energy resources. Data was gathered from scientific articles, official statistical reports, and economic analyses.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the current global economy, achieving sustainable development, the rational use of resources, and environmental protection are pressing issues. According to the World Bank, 50% of global GDP, amounting to \$44 trillion in 2023, depends on nature and biodiversity. In response to this, the World Bank allocated \$26 million in 2023 to address climate change-related challenges in developing countries.

International efforts to support the green economy are also reflected in Uzbekistan. Notably, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the State Program for the Implementation of the Strategy “Uzbekistan - 2030” in the Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on “Approval of the Interim Regulation on the Procedure for the Implementation of Projects on International Greenhouse Gas Trading”, and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on “Approval of the National Green Economy Taxonomy”—along with many other regulatory legal acts contribute to the promotion of the green economy.

Uzbekistan, a lower-middle-income country in Asia, has a Green Growth Index of 38.66.¹

Figure 1. Green Growth Index.

1 <https://ggindex-simtool.gggi.org>

There are many pressing issues in our country regarding energy efficiency and resource conservation. For instance, 98% of the electricity produced comes from thermal and hydroelectric power plants. This results in significant consumption of non-renewable resources, including water and fuel. Only 3% of the total energy is generated from solar and wind energy.

Figure 2. Total types of electricity generated in 2023 (in percent).

No	The total amount of electricity produced	78005mkw/h
1.	Hydroelectric power plants	52367,1 mkw/h
2.	Solar power plants	1237,3 mkw/h
3.	Wind power plants	7,2 mkw/h
4.	Thermal power plants	24393,4 mkw/h

According to calculations, by 2030, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan is expected to reach 41 million, and our economy is expected to grow 1.5 times. In 2030, 120 billion kWh of electricity will be required, and in 2035 – 135 billion kWh. That is, 1.7 times more than now. To meet this demand for electricity, additional power plants are planned to be built. By 2030, 50% of the total demand for electricity is planned to be covered by solar power plants. Our government plans to upgrade 27 GW of energy sources by 2030, 40% of which will be based on renewable energy sources. Uzbekistan has significant renewable energy resources. The technical potential of solar and wind energy in the country is estimated to be several times greater than the entire primary energy supply. Solar radiation is on par with countries such as Greece, Singapore, Portugal, Spain, and higher than in Italy or China.

The main directions of state policy in the field of renewable energy sources are: setting priority areas and implementing measures in the field of renewable energy sources; developing and implementing state programs and other programs in the field of renewable energy sources; strengthening the country's energy security, diversifying the part of the fuel and energy balance related to the production of electricity, heat energy, and biogas using renewable energy sources; promoting the introduction of innovative technologies, scientific and technical developments in the field of renewable energy sources, increasing the energy efficiency of renewable energy sources, expanding their production and localization; improving organizational and legal mechanisms for attracting business entities to create energy production capacities based on proven technologies for the use of renewable energy sources; providing state support and incentives for producers of energy from renewable energy sources, as well as manufacturers of renewable energy sources equipment.

In 2022, the Asian Development Bank approved a \$500 million loan to help our government finance business support, social protection, and food security. To improve water and food security in Uzbekistan, ADB also approved a \$150 million loan and a \$3 million grant that year. To increase renewable energy sources and energy efficiency, the bank signed an agreement with the private sector to build a 500-megawatt wind farm in the city of Zarafshan.

Many of the solar projects are located in the southern and southwestern regions of Uzbekistan, where global horizontal irradiation is highest and the prices achieved are competitive. Additionally, there are several small hydroelectric power plants.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-156, dated May 12, 2023, "On Measures to Introduce the System of 'Green Energy' Certificates," was adopted. In accordance with the resolution, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Ministry of Energy, and the "Uzbekgidroenergo" Joint-Stock Company will gradually introduce a system of "green energy" certificates confirming that electricity is produced using renewable sources. The implementation timeline is as follows: from July 1, 2023 – for electricity produced at hydroelectric power plants within the system of "Uzbekgidroenergo" Joint-Stock Company; from October 1, 2023 – for electricity produced at solar, wind, and hydroelectric power plants, as well as using other renewable energy sources.

Currently, 13 projects are underway to build "green" power plants and energy storage systems in collaboration with companies from Saudi Arabia, the UAE, China, France, and Switzerland. In particular, by 2025, it is planned to: increase the total capacity of solar power plants to 2.9 gigawatts, increase the total capacity of wind power plants to 900 megawatts, launch energy storage devices with a capacity of 400 megawatts.

In recent years, the government has been implementing a wide range of measures aimed at conserving and rationally using natural resources while supporting the development of ecological sustainability. These initiatives are designed to promote an ecological lifestyle and enhance the environmental image of various sectors of the country's economy. Such efforts significantly impact the sustainable development of the regions.

Below, we will touch upon some prospects for cooperation.

Cooperation relations between the Republic of South Korea and the Republic of Uzbekistan were established on December 11, 2024. A meeting was held at the Ministry of Economy and Finance with representatives of the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) and the Korea International Cooperation Agency (KOICA) to discuss the development of the green economy.

The primary purpose of the meeting was to discuss future work within the framework of the agreement "On Support for the Transition to a Green Economy," signed between the Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Global Green Growth Institute. Within the framework of this project, a total of 6.5 million US dollars in KOICA grant funds is planned to be allocated.

Figure 2: Analysis of funds attracted by international financial organizations and green investments in 2021.²

International public finance flows from international financial institutions are the most important source of financing for development projects in Uzbekistan. The country meets the established criteria for obtaining grants and concessional loans for development financing.

Following the latest round of reforms, international interest in Uzbekistan has significantly increased. Consequently, policy advice and technical assistance from international development finance institutions, particularly in the area of public financial management, will benefit Uzbekistan's efforts to develop the private sector and implement a green transition.

As of October 1, 2024, the World Bank's program in Uzbekistan consists of 24 active projects with a total value of approximately \$4.7 billion. These projects are financed by: \$3.4 billion in concessional loans from the International Development Association (IDA), accounting for over 70% of all financing provided by the bank to the country. \$1 billion in loans from the International Development Bank and the Development Bank (IDB, which is part of the World Bank).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Energy resources are decreasing every year. Therefore, the use of renewable energy sources is considered a cost-effective alternative. The adoption of renewable energy reduces production costs and has a lesser negative impact on the environment. To ensure environmental sustainability and increase the green growth index, it is essential to support green energy initiatives in Uzbekistan to mitigate the negative consequences of climate change.

The following recommendations are relevant to preventing such negative impacts: monitoring state budget expenditures to ensure compliance with sustainable development goals. Allocating subsidies or providing preferential loans for the creation of renewable energy sources. Introducing incentives in fiscal policy for entrepreneurs using green energy, which will help support the green economy.

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